

Prioritizing areas for strategic management against Extreme Wildfire Events in the Iberian Peninsula using Pan-European datasets

AHP - Pairwise comparisons

This study aims to inform prioritization of forested areas to be managed at the Iberian Peninsula level, using Pan-European datasets, in view of the risk of wildfires. The objective of making this study a participatory work is to integrate heterogeneous knowledge in highlighting the most important criteria for decision making by involving experts and professionals working on different parts of the FIRE-RES project.

The purpose of this survey is to compile experts' opinions to assess the relevance of the criteria and sub-criteria selected to prioritize those areas.

For that, a pairwise comparison is employed among the criteria and sub-criteria, resulting afterwards, in a percentage of relevance for each. This will facilitate the prioritization of areas to be managed.

Estimated time to complete this survey ~10 minutes.

* Indicates required question

Note on anonymity: Your personal and contact details will not be published anywhere. If any findings from this survey are published, you will never be mentioned by name and your verbatim responses will not be attributed to you personally.

1. Email address *
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Establishing shared definitions: Brief descriptions of the criteria

- **Fire behavior:** Refers to the manner in which fire reacts to the variables of the environment, including fuels, weather, and topography. The aim is to detect the areas with the worst potential fire behavior, so that they receive higher priority for management.
- **Fuels:** The goal of this criterion is to select which biometric variables are most relevant to manage and that will influence more positively when it comes to prevention and suppression efforts. We assume that presenting higher canopy cover percentage, lower crown base height, higher crown bulk density and higher biomass, should be given more priority than the opposite.
- **Values at risk:** We assume that shorter distances to high population density areas, proximity to main roads and being part of protected areas should be given higher priority.

Criteria weighting

How would you rank the criteria in terms of the impact they should have on the selection of priority areas for management?

Please, fill out the survey indicating the **relative importance of each criterion in comparison to the others**. See the accompanying image for an explanation of the numerical scale (the same applies to the sub-criteria).

Example:

Selecting the 7 on the left would mean that you feel that Criterion A is **strongly more relevant** than Criterion B.

Instead, selecting the 5 on the right would mean that you feel that Criterion B is **more relevant** than Criterion A.

Criterion A				vs.	Criterion B			
Extremely relevant	Strongly more relevant	More relevant	Slightly more relevant		Slightly more relevant	More relevant	Strongly more relevant	Extremely relevant
(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>						

2. **Fuels** vs. **Values at risk ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

3. **Fire behavior** vs. **Fuels ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

4. **Values at risk** vs. **Fire behavior ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

Assessment of the sub-criteria related to 'Values at risk'

- **Population Density:** Higher priority to areas near densely populated zones.
- **Distance to Main Roads:** Higher priority to areas close to main roads, both for accessibility of firefighters and ignition risk.
- **Protected Areas:** Binary—whether the area is within a protected zone (maximum priority), or not (no priority).

Please, rank now their relevance compared to each other.

5. **Population density** vs. **Protected areas ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

6. **Population density** vs. **Distance to main roads ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

7. **Distance to main roads** vs. **Protected areas ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

Assessment of the sub-criteria related to 'Fire behavior'

- **Rate of Spread:** Higher priority to areas with faster potential fire spread.
- **Flame Length:** Higher priority to areas with greater expected flame length.
- **Fireline Intensity:** Higher priority to areas with higher projected fireline intensity.

8. **Flame length** vs. **Rate of spread ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

9. **Flame length** vs. **Fire line intensity ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

10. **Fire line intensity** vs. **Rate of spread ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

Assessment of the sub-criterion related to 'Fuels'

- **Above-Ground Biomass:** Higher priority to areas with more biomass (more fuel).
- **Crown Base Height:** Higher priority to areas with lower crown base height (higher crown fire risk).
- **Canopy Cover:** Higher priority to areas with denser canopy cover (facilitates crown fire spread).
- **Crown Bulk Density:** Higher priority to areas with greater crown bulk density (sustains crown fires).

11. **Above ground biomass** vs. **Crown base height ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

12. **Crown bulk density** vs. **Canopy cover ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

13. **Above ground biomass** vs. **Canopy cover ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

14. **Crown bulk density** vs. **Crown base height ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

15. **Above ground biomass** vs. **Crown bulk density ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

16. **Canopy cover** vs. **Crown base height ***

Mark only one oval per row.

	(9)	(7)	(5)	(3)	Equal (1)	(3)	(5)	(7)	(9)
.	<input type="radio"/>								

Suggestions for **future** potential indicators that better address our selected criteria

In this final section, we invite participants to suggest potential indicators that could help us improve the sub-criteria used to characterize the 'Values at Risk' criterion in future assessments. We are particularly interested in indicators that reflect social, cultural, or ecological values, provided that harmonized datasets are available across Europe, as with the data used throughout this study.

- 17. Do you have any suggestions for additional indicators to characterize the criterion 'Values at risk'?

Please list them down

- 18. We are at the end of this survey! Do you have any other comments or suggestions?

THANK YOU
for your participation!

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